

The Ni^{II} complexes exhibited three bands at 10 420, 16 950 and 24 390 cm⁻¹ for HBBH and at 10 310, 16 670 and 23 810 cm⁻¹ for HMBBH complexes, respectively. Spectral data of the Ni^{II} complexes with HBBH and HMBBH and observed moments of 2.94 and 2.96 B.M., respectively, conform the octahedral configuration with two unpaired electrons. The values of 10 Dq, B', β and nephelauxetic ratio β° have been calculated for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes and the values are found to lie in the same order, i.e. 10 420 cm⁻¹, 932 cm⁻¹, 0.882, 11.8, and 11 930 cm⁻¹, 847 cm⁻¹, 0.872 and 12.8 for the HBBH and HMBBH complexes, respectively. The ν₂/ν₁ ratio for the HBBH and HMBBH complexes fall in the range 2.15–2.18 (Co complex) and 1.61–1.62 (Ni complex) which is characteristic of octahedral geometry¹⁸.

The Cu–HBBH complex showed weak band at 10 870, 14 080 and 15 630 cm⁻¹ and the Cu–HMBBH complex showed bands at 11 110, 14 490 and 16 130 cm⁻¹. The ratio σ₁/σ₂ for the above two complexes is 1.22 and 1.36, respectively, indicating distorted octahedral geometry. Magnetic moment values of the Cu^{II} complexes are 1.94 and 1.96 B.M., respectively.

All the complexes formed by HBBH and HMBBH start losing water at 100° and the hydration is complete at 300°. The loss in weight corresponds to the elimination of two molecules of water.

Acknowledgement

The authors' thanks are due to U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Research Fellowship to one of them (H.R.S.) and to the University of Allahabad for facilities.

References

1. R. L. DUTTA and MD. M. HUSSAIN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1985, **44**, 635.
2. E. SORKING, W. ROTH and H. EARLENMEYER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **35**, 1736.
3. A. SHYAMAL and S. KALE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 46.
4. M. MASHIMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1962, **35**, 332, 338, 2020.
5. S. BURCHETT and C. E. MELOAIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1207.
6. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1978.
7. G. MUKHERJEE, S. N. PODDAR and K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 275.
8. M. A. ALI and R. BOSE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **29**, 265.
9. J. R. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibration of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York 1971.
10. P. V. RAO, N. R. RAO, V. J. T. RAJU and M. G. GANORKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 482.
11. N. N. GREENWOOD and A. EARNSHAW, "Chemistry of Elements", Pergamon, London, 1985.
12. M. C. DAY, JR. and J. SELBIN, "Theoretical Inorganic Chemistry", East-West Press, New Delhi, 1971.
13. N. SAHA and N. MUKHERJEE, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 1135.

Interaction of Divalent Metal Ions with Uracil. Part-II. Uracil Complexes of Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II)

A. R. SARKAR*, R. K. BANDYOPADHYAY

and

P. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 12 August 1987, revised 2 May 1988,
accepted 17 May 1988

URACIL, a constituent of RNA, exists in the dilactum form both in the solid state and in neutral aqueous solution but has been infrequently used in complexation. Uracil in its neutral form coordinates to the metal ions^{1,2} through the oxygen, but under basic condition in its anionic form it may coordinate to the metal ion both through oxygen and nitrogen atoms. The preparation and characterisation of oxygen coordinated uracil complexes of divalent metal ions have been reported³. In this paper we report the isolation and characterisation of some new complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with uracil in its anionic form coordinating through its nitrogen.

Uracil

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of complexes. General method: Calculated amount of uracil dissolved in methanol was added to the methanolic solutions of the respective metal chloride (except in case of iron, FeSO₄·7H₂O was used); the ratio of metal–uracil being 1 : 2 and pH maintained around 10 by adding dilute NaOH solution. The mixtures were refluxed for 10 h when respective crystals separated out. It was separated by filtration and washed with methanol. Thermogravimetric were recorded with a Derivatograph (System : F. Paulik, J. Paulik, L. Erdey, MOM, Budapest). The electronic spectra of the solid complexes were recorded with a Carl Zeiss DMR 21 spectrophotometer and the ir spectra (KBr) with a Perkin–Elmer 257 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are coloured, insoluble in water but soluble in non-polar solvents like CCl₄, indicating their non-electrolytic behaviour. Analytical data (Table 1) correspond to the formula ML₂(H₂O)₄, where M=Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II};

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} ** B.M.
		M	N	
MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Khaki	15.92 (15.74)	16.68 (16.05)	5.96
FeL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Yellowish brown	16.20 (15.96)	16.46 (16.00)	5.20
CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Reddish brown	16.63 (16.70)	15.92 (15.87)	4.62
NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Green	16.68 (16.64)	16.00 (15.88)	3.24
CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄	Blue	17.89 (17.77)	15.81 (15.66)	1.96

*L=C₄H₃N₂O₃.
**At 308 K.

L=C₄H₃N₂O₃⁻. The copper complex starts decomposing at 130° and continues to lose weight upto 450° without any intermediate. The observed weight loss at 450° corresponds to the conversion of CuL₂(H₂O)₄ to CuO.

The iron(II) complex exhibits a doublet weak absorption band at 8 650 and 10 750 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned due to ⁵E_g←⁵T_{2g} transition. The doublet arises because the degeneracy of the E_g level is being lifted by Jahn – Teller and tetragonal distortions⁴. For the cobalt(II) complex the weak absorption band around 8 150, 16 200 cm⁻¹ and the strong band at 19 550 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to transitions ⁴T_{2g}←⁴T_{1g} (ν₁), ⁴A_{2g}←⁴T_{1g} (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g} (P)←⁴T_{1g} (ν₃) respectively. The medium broad band around 8 650 cm⁻¹, the medium band around 13 980 cm⁻¹ and the strong sharp band at 26 050 cm⁻¹ of the nickel(II) complex may be assigned to the ³T_{2g}←³A_{2g} (ν₁), ³T_{1g}←³A_{2g} (ν₂) and ³T_{1g} (P)←³A_{2g} (ν₃) transitions, respectively. The medium broad band at 15 160 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the spin-forbidden⁴ transitions ¹E_g←³A_{2g}. The value of Δ in the cobalt(II) complex is 8 050 cm⁻¹ and that in the nickel(II) complex is 8 650 cm⁻¹ indicating their octahedral stereochemistry. In comparison to oxygen coordinated uracil complexes⁵, the value of Δ in this case is higher by about 500 cm⁻¹. A strong broad band at 14 020 cm⁻¹ for the copper(II) complex refers its octahedral geometry.

The main area of interest in the ir spectra is in the region 1 800–1 300 cm⁻¹ where the ν_{C=O} and δ_{NH} bands of uracil is located. The position and intensity of the band due to the ν_{C(2)=O} and δ_{NH(1)} remain almost unaltered in the complexes with respect to that of the free uracil⁵. The position of the band due to ν_{C(4)=O+C=C} is shifted very little while that due to δ_{NH(3)} disappears completely in the complexes. The disappearance of the δ_{NH(3)} band in the complexes indicates that the coordination of the uracil in its anionic form to the metal ion takes place through N(3).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the University of Kalyani for providing a Research Fellowship to one of them (R.K.B.).

References

1. M. GOODGAME and K. W. JOHNS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, 30, L835.
2. M. GUPTA and M. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Polyhedron*, 1985, 4, 475.
3. A. R. SARKAR and P. GHOSH, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, 78, L89.
4. A. B. P. LEVYER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1967, p. 87.
5. H. SUSI and J. S. ARD, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1971, 27, 1549.

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Transition Metal Complexes with Salicylaldiminobiacetyl Monohydrazone

E. M. SUBRAMANIAN, V. DURAI

and

S. BALASUBRAMANIAN*

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, A. O. College Campus, University of Madras, Madras-600 026

Manuscript received 24 August 1987, revised 25 April 1988, accepted 28 May 1988

CONJUGATED azomethine compound, viz. rhodopsin¹ is an important intermediate in the chemistry of vision. The *o*-hydroxyarylidine Schiff bases which are in the form of pyridoxal derivatives², are involved in transamination and racemisation reactions of α-amino acids. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of the complexes of bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn with the Schiff base salicylaldiminobiacetyl monohydrazone (SALBAMH) (1) derived from biacetyl monohydrazone and 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde.

Experimental

Biacetyl (Fluka) was vacuum-distilled before use. 2-Hydroxy benzaldehyde was also distilled. Hydrazine hydrate (98–100%, B.D.H.) was dehydrated following the reported procedure³. Nitrogen was estimated by the micro-Kjeldahl method. Nickel and cobalt were determined by spectrophotometrically, copper by solvent extraction method and manganese and zinc complexometrically. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Shimadzu IR 408 spectrophotometer and electronic